

The Burden and Awareness of Hepatitis B Virus Infection among the Patient Attending OPD in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Bihar

Ankur Kumar¹, Ajay Kumar², Arun Kumar Sinha³, Rajesh Prasad⁴

¹SMO and Infection Control Officer, Department of Central Pathology, BMIMSH Pawapuri, Bihar, India

²Deputy Medical Superintendent, BMIMSH Pawapuri, Bihar, India

³Medical Superintendent and Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, BMIMSH Pawapuri, Bihar, India

⁴SMO, Department of Central Pathology, BMIMSH Pawapuri, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Ankur Kumar

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Abstract:

Introduction: Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection prevalence is believed to be elevated in Bihar, India; however, state-wide prevalence data are not available. An understanding of HBV prevalence, risk factors and genotype distribution can be used to plan control measures in Bihar.

Material & Method: A prospective, OPD-based serosurvey was conducted from January 2024 to June 2024 at BMIMSH Pawapuri, Bihar. Children aged ≥ 5 years and adults were eligible to participate. Demographic and risk behavior data were collected, and serological specimens were obtained and tested for Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg).

Result: 5,546 OPD patients participated in the study shows HBV prevalence of 2.29%. HBsAg positivity was most prevalent in the 40–49 year-old and 30–39 year-old age groups (29.92% and 24.41% respectively). The mean age of positive patients was 44.8 years with the majority (approx 30%) of positive cases in the 40–49 years age group. Sex wise distribution shows that there was slight female preponderance. Out of total number of positive cases (127), 71 (55.90%) were females and 56 (44.09%) were males. Among all positive cases having a history of Diabetes, hypertension, Chronic Renal Failure and Cancer were 3.15%, 3.94%, 0.79% and 0.79%.

Conclusion: The study findings, including the overall prevalence of chronic HBV infection, associated risk factors and demographic characteristics can guide prevention and control efforts, including treatment provision. In addition to high-risk populations, efforts targeting rural areas and adults aged 40 would be the most effective for identifying infected individuals.

Keywords: HBV, HBsAg, Seroprevalance.

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Introduction

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is a partially double-stranded DNA virus belonging to the genus Orthohepadnavirus and family Hepadnaviridae [1]. Hepatitis B virus (HBV), is one of the blood borne viruses that cause notifiable diseases, which consume health resources and have public health implications. HBV specifically attacks the liver and can cause both acute and chronic diseases. It is estimated that globally there are 296 million people who are chronically infected with HBV [2].

HBV transmitted predominantly in high endemicity areas by perinatal transmission or vertical transmission (from mother to child at birth) and in low-endemicity areas HBV is primarily transferred by horizontal transmission (transmission among individuals of the same generation) by close contact between children has also been documented and is strongly linked to high-risk behaviors such

as unprotected sex and injectable drug use [3] Antiviral therapy has decreased the rates of liver decompensation and, as a result, lowered hospitalization and mortality rates. The longer-term benefits of antiviral therapy may include reversing liver fibrosis, reducing the risk of developing hepatocellular carcinoma, and decreasing the number of patients requiring liver transplantation [4,5,6]

Globally, an estimated 257–400 million people have chronic HBV infection [7,8,9] and estimated 29% of cirrhosis-related deaths worldwide were due to HBV(10). Now Hepatitis B ranks as the 15th leading cause of death worldwide [11]. India ranks in the intermediate endemic zone for the HBV and prevalence of 3–4.2% of Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) and 40 million HBV carriers in the world [12]. The Global Health Sector Strategy

on viral hepatitis (2016–2021) endorsed by the World Health Assembly in 2016 [12] called for the elimination of viral hepatitis as a public health threat by 2030. Bihar, an north-eastern state of India, has high percentage of tribal population in the country and limited information is available regarding the prevalence of HBsAg. The present study was undertaken to estimate the seroprevalence of HBsAg among the patient attending in OPD of BMIMSH Pawapuri, Bihar situated at north-eastern state of India.

Aims and Objectives

From the study we had conclude about -

- To estimate the seroprevalence of HBsAg among the patient attending in OPD of BMIMSH Pawapuri, Bihar situated at north-eastern state of India.
- To know associated risk factors and their demographic characteristics.
- To help policy makers for formulating appropriate control strategies against Hepatitis B virus.

Materials and Methods

Type of Study -This was a hospital lab based prospective study.

Period of study - Study conducted from January 2024 to June 2024 (6 months).

Place of study - Central lab, Microbiology department, BMIMSH PAWAPURI.

Age: Children aged ≥ 5 years and adults were eligible to participate in this study.

Gender: No gender specification.

Methodology:

2ml blood sample was drawn in a serum separator tube from patient attending OPD who were visited first time in BMIMSH, Pawapuri Bihar irrespective of previous HBsAg status, after taking consent from patient, or from his/her parents if he/she not able to give consent. These samples collected at

sample collection unit and sent to Central lab, Microbiology department for further study. Within one hour of collection, the samples were centrifuged for 15 minutes at 3,000 revolutions per minute and were tested for Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg). Unused blood was disposed of as per healthcare waste management guidelines and all specimens were destroyed following completion of the study.

Demographic and risk behavior data were also collected by survey questionnaire, after obtaining informed consent. The study questionnaire was administered as a face-to-face interview and if needed by telephonic mode also about socio-demographic data, medical history, lifestyle information.

Data Analysis & Results

There were a total of 5,546 samples collected from different OPD attending patients who agreed to participate in the study.

Different results and socio-demographic characteristics of this study were analysed and shown in Table (1-5) and Figure (1-5).

Out of 5,546 OPD patients tested 127 were found positive for HBsAg and shows the prevalence of HBsAg. The overall prevalence of HBsAg was 2.29% ($5,546/127 \times 100$) as shown in Figure 1.

HBsAg positivity was most prevalent in the 40–49 year-old and 30–39 year-old age groups (29.92% and 24.41% respectively) as shown in Table 1 and Figure 3. The mean age of positive patients was 44.8 years with the majority (approx 30%) of positive cases in the 40–49 years age group as shown in Figure 3. Sex wise distribution shows that there was slight female preponderance. Out of total number of positive cases (127), 71 (55.90%) were females and 56 (44.09%) were males as shown in Figure 2.

In this study among all positive cases having a history of Diabetes, hypertension, Chronic Renal Failure and Cancer were 3.15%, 3.94%, 0.79% and 0.79% respectively as shown in Table 2-5.

Figure 1: Seropositivity of HBsAg

Demographic characteristics and risk factors associated among HBsAg seropositive patients (n=127) described in Figure (2-3) and Table (1-5)

Figure 2- Distribution of HBsAg seropositive cases according to sex n=127

Table 1: Distribution of HBsAg seropositive cases according to Age group n=127

Age Group (years)	HBsAg positive n (%)
5-18	06 (4.72%)
19-29	11 (8.66%)
30-39	31 (24.41%)
40-49	38 (29.92%)
50-59	29 (22.83%)
>=60	12 (9.45%)

Figure 3- Comparison of HBsAg positivity with different Age group

Table 2: Distribution of HBsAg seropositive cases according to Diabetes status n=127

Diabetes status	n (%)
Yes	04 (3.15%)
No	123 (96.85%)

Table 3: Distribution of HBsAg seropositive cases according to hypertension status n=127

Hypertension status	n (%)
Yes	05 (3.94%)
No	122 (96.06%)

Table 4: Distribution of HBsAg seropositive cases according to Chronic Renal Failure status n=127

Chronic Renal Failure	n (%)
Yes	01 (0.79%)
No	126 (99.21%)

Table 5: Distribution of HBsAg seropositive cases according to Cancer status n=127

Cancer status	n (%)
Yes	01 (0.79%)
No	126 (99.21%)

Discussion

This study, the assessing the prevalence of HBsAg in Pawapuri region of Bihar state. Mathematical models shown in Murhekar et al. study in 2020 [13] helped to classify the endemicity of HBsAg as well as to quantify the burden of HBV infection. The prevalence study of HBsAg in different parts of the country by Bhattacharya et al. in 2015 [14]; Sharma et al. in 2019 [15]; and Manjiyil and Konikkara, in 2021[16] was higher than the HBsAg prevalence reported from our study (2.29%).

Previous study by National Family Health Survey 4- Factsheet 2021(17) as a part of National Program for Surveillance of Viral Hepatitis, shown that National seroprevalence of Hepatitis B was 0.95% (0.89-1.01) which was lower than the prevalence reported from our study (2.29%). Seroprevalence was highest in group 1(Andhra Pradesh and Telangana) [2.39% (1.97-2.89)], while in group 2 (Bihar, Jharkhand, West Bengal and Andan Nicobar) was [1.26% (1.05-1.49)]; unlike to our study, National Family Health Survey 4- Factsheet 2021[17] study have higher seroprevalence among men than women. This may be due to in our study among the participants, there were more women (53.8%) than men (46.2%). Like to our study seroprevalence had shown an increase with advancing age. Seroprevalence was lower amongst those who were administered safe injections. Subjects with higher-risk sexual intercourse had shown greater seroprevalence [1.32% (0.86-1.78)] than those without higher risk sexual intercourse [1.03% (0.96-1.1)].

Our study is subject to several limitations. First, we were not able to independently verify any of the responses on the questionnaire. Also, we could not determine the number of nonresponders. As with any cross-sectional study that examines a chronic condition, it is challenging to attribute risk due to lack of temporality, as the HBV infection could have occurred at any time during the lifetime of the study subjects. The sampling method of this study, which included patient attending in OPD of BMIMSH Pawapuri, could lead to potential selection bias. Persons living together are more likely to exhibit similar behaviors and could lead to disproportionate risks in the sample that may not be representative of the general population. Additionally, the sampling method of our study was not designed to produce precise per-region prevalence estimates; there was a preponderance of patient attending in OPD of BMIMSH Pawapuri were found to have a high prevalence of HBV than general residents. Thus these results should be interpreted with caution, as this could lead to overestimation of the prevalence in these areas.

Conclusion

The data presented in this study will provide a baseline for planning purposes and will help get an initial understanding of HBV disease burden in Pawapuri region of Bihar. In order to monitor the trends and spread of Hepatitis B, we intent to collect robust data at regular intervals for better understanding of the epidemiology of Hepatitis B.

Proposed Program Implementation Strategy as per the analysis Focused interventions (awareness, screening, and treatment services) are required in these areas for Hepatitis B prevalence study.

Need to establish an inbuilt component of continuous surveillance as a part of the program through existing mechanisms.

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